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Crisp Set Qualitative Comparative Analysis of Snow and Ice Control Policies around the World

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Abstract

A huge amount of public money is spent on winter road maintenance (WRM) across the globe in the countries witnessing heavy and medium snowfall. Most of the developed countries have developed efficient means of carrying out WRM operations, but, some countries have inefficient policies for carrying out winter road maintenance operations in place, resulting in chaos owing to public inconvenience. The situation gets alarming when a particular snowfall event continues for two consecutive days resulting in a snow depth of 4–5 feet. The ill prepared snow removal teams face a tough time during the clearance operations, given the non-availability of efficient WRM practices. In such scenarios, it is possible for a country struggling with WRM to adapt / borrow the policies of those countries having efficient mechanism in place pertaining to snow clearance. In this study, we carry out a comparative policy analysis using a set theoretic approach called crisp set Qualitative Comparative Analysis (csQCA). A total of 10 countries have been studied on account of winter maintenance policies and a comparative assessment is carried out. Also, the winter road maintenance practices in Kashmir valley are studied. The presence or absence of various conditions result in an altogether different outcome. csQCA provides with a logical conclusion with regard to the factors responsible for effective winter road maintenance. It is observed that intersection policy (POLC) and road weather information system (RWIS) and technological intervention (TECH) are responsible for effective WRM.

Keywords: csQCA, Comparative policy analysis, Winter road maintenance

1. Introduction

Winter road maintenance (WRM) operations present a number of decision-making challenges at the strategic, tactical, operational, and real-time levels. The complexity associated with the winter maintenance is being amplified in the presence of visible climate change across the globe. Winter road maintenance is a highly uncertain phenomenon given the uncertainty associated with weather and climate change. It has been reported that the rising global temperatures have increased the frequency and intensity of extreme snowfall events in a number of regions around the world. (Donat et al. 2016). Avalanches are frequently caused by continuous heavy snowfall over a higher topographical region, resulting in significant economic losses. Avalanches are a common natural disaster in Kashmir due to the area's complex topography (Mishra 2015). A devastating avalanche struck Kashmir in 1895, claiming many lives and destroying much property. Around 150 people were killed, and over 500 homes were damaged (Lawrence 1895). Between November and April, a large portion of Kashmir receives snowfall.

WRM encompasses a complex set of activities for road maintenance in icy and snowy conditions, which frequently differ between countries. WRM activities include, for example, mechanical and manual snow removal, deicing with a mixture of road salt and crushed stone aggregate, the use of anti-icing chemicals, the dissemination of traveler information, and so on. The northern United States, Canada, Sweden, Finland, Norway, the United Kingdom, the Netherlands, Germany, and Japan have the most prominent WRM practices (Glavic, Mladenovic, and Stevanovic 2016). The winter road maintenance in Kashmir valley is carried out by snow clearance control rooms established by Mechanical Engineering Department, Kashmir in various sub divisions. The Mechanical Engineering Department, Kashmir is a sub department working under the administration control of Public Works Department, PW (R&B) Department. The concerned control rooms hold a fleet of imported and inland snow removal machinery on their inventory.

In this study, we present a comparative analysis of policies of snow clearance / winter road maintenance, prevalent in different parts of the world. We use crisp set qualitative comparative analysis (csQCA) approach to compare the winter maintenance practices in various countries – USA, Canada, France, Germany, China, Japan, Hungary, Italy, Netherlands, Norway and Kashmir (India).

2. Literature Review

The literature on snow and ice control policies around the world reveals a diverse range of approaches aimed at mitigating the impacts of winter weather conditions on transportation and public safety. Several studies have focused on the effectiveness of different de-icing agents, such as salt and sand, in preventing accidents and maintaining road conditions during snow and ice events. For instance, (Shi and O’Keefe 2005) found that a combination of pre-wetted salt and anti-icing strategies led to significantly reduced accidents on icy roads in a case study of a northern US state. Additionally, research has explored the importance of winter weather forecasting and communication systems in guiding timely policy decisions and informing the public about hazardous road conditions. Studies by (Dey, Mishra, and Chowdhury 2014) and (Uccellini and Ten Hoeve 2019) highlight how accurate and timely weather forecasts, coupled with efficient communication channels, can improve preparedness and response to winter storms, ultimately minimizing economic losses and enhancing road safety.

Despite the valuable insights provided by existing research, there remain notable gaps in the literature on snow and ice control policies. First, while many studies have focused on the effectiveness of specific de-icing agents and their application methods, there is a lack of comparative analyses that examine the combination of factors contributing to successful policies across different regions and climates. A more holistic approach that considers the interaction between various policy elements could provide a comprehensive understanding of best practices in snow and ice control. Furthermore, although research has explored the impact of winter weather forecasting, little attention has been given to the role of public awareness campaigns and education initiatives. Understanding how these campaigns influence public behavior and cooperation with snow and ice control measures could be instrumental in enhancing policy effectiveness. To address these gaps, this literature review aims to conduct a Crisp Set Qualitative Comparative Analysis (csQCA) to identify the necessary and sufficient conditions for successful snow and ice control policies in diverse geographic contexts. By integrating and analyzing a broad range of studies, this review seeks to offer a comprehensive perspective on policy design and implementation to promote safety and resilience in winter weather conditions globally.

3. Research Methodology

This study involves the comparison of winter road maintenance policies in many countries with that in Kashmir valley. Therefore, it is imperative to use some tool which will enable us to compare winter maintenance policies across the globe. Accordingly, after a thorough search from the existing literature on ‘comparative policy analysis’, we came across a very useful tool known as ‘Qualitative

Comparative Analysis (QCA)'. Set Theoretic QCA methodology is a set of systematic methods for studying causality in a simple data table of binary or ordinal variables. It is most commonly used in comparative research, with qualitative data, or as part of case-study research methods. QCA assists in determining both necessary and sufficient causality in small samples of $N=8$ to $N=200$. QCA provides formal methods for analyzing qualitative data about the characteristics and contextual backgrounds of these cases. QCA was proposed by (Ragin,1987) as a configurational research method that combines the strengths of qualitative (case-oriented) and quantitative (variable-oriented) research methods. Furthermore, QCA analysis can examine the similarities and differences between a set of comparable cases to identify the structural conditions that lead to an outcome. Among different set theoretic versions of QCA, csQCA is thought to be more appropriate than fsQCA. One of the most significant advantages of QCA is its ability to identify equifinality or multiple conjunctural causation, i.e., QCA allows for the assessment of complex causation between different combinations of causal conditions resulting in the same outcome. QCA has gained broader acceptance across various research disciplines due to its ability to identify combinations of necessary and sufficient condition(s). Another reason for using QCA as a technique for comparing winter maintenance in various countries, is that it is systematic, which means that it successfully uses formal logic to compare cases, explore causal diversity, and reduces the wealth of case information to achieve parsimony through minimization using Boolean logic.

3.1 Crisp Set Qualitative Comparative Analysis

QCA is made up of two configurational approaches, each of which is based on set theory. To analyze cases, one method employs crisp-sets (dichotomous variables, 0s and 1s). The other method makes use of fuzzy sets. Although the use of fuzzy-sets has increased in recent years, the use of crisp sets and the csQCA as described by (Ragin 1987) is still used in the vast majority of empirical applications (Rihoux et al. 2013). For this study, csQCA is being used, and the various steps involved in performing csQCA, as stated by (Marx, Cambré, and Rihoux 2013), are depicted in Figure 1. For

Figure 1. Flow chart for csQCA (Adapted from Marx et al., 2013)

the purpose of carrying out csQCA, a host of open source tools are available like TOSMANA, fuzzy, fsQCA, Add-In for Excel. For the sake of simplicity, we have used the Add-In for Excel (Cronqvist, 2019) for carrying out the csQCA.

3.2 Data Tables

Development of a data matrix is the first step in carrying out csQCA study. It involves representation various variables and the outcome in the form of columns, the cases are represented by rows. The

presence of a factor in a case is shown as 1 (one) and the absence of the same is represented by 0 (zero). The outcome is also represented by 1 or 0 depending upon whether the outcome is positive or negative. Based on the review of various policies for WRM in different countries, in this study we have considered only five causal factors- POLC: Strong policy, WINX: Good Winter Index, RWIS: Efficient Road Weather Information System, ANTI: Best Anti-Icing treatment practices, TECH: Use of relevant technology and the outcome as EWRM: Effective Winter Road Maintenance. The choice of using these five causal factors for csQCA is that all these factors have been observed common in all the countries as responsible for efficient snow removal operations. A strong policy refers to robust and resilient policy which keeps on delivering the objectives of the policy (safe roads, effective and efficient snow removal) irrespective of the weather condition (depth of snow and weather conditions). Winter severity index helps in planning for materials and consumables (fuel etc.). RWIS, anti-icing and technology also result in effective and efficient WRM.

Country	POLC	WINX	RWIS	ANTI	TECH	EWRM
USA	1	1	1	1	1	1
Canada	0	1	1	1	1	1
France	0	1	1	1	1	1
Germany	1	1	1	1	1	1
China	0	0	1	1	1	1
Japan	1	0	0	1	1	1
Hungary	1	0	1	1	1	1
Italy	1	1	0	1	1	1
Netherlands	0	0	1	1	1	1
Norway	1	1	0	1	1	1
Kashmir (India)	0	0	0	1	0	0

Figure 2. Data Matrix of "Effective WRM" and Five Conditions

3.3 Results and Discussions

In this section we discuss about the results obtained by executing the data tables using csQCA methodology. The effectiveness of the winter road maintenance is observed as depending upon various causal factors – a combination of strong policy (POLC) and an efficient road weather information system (RWIS) which is observed in the case of Kashmir. Next, it is the lack of relevant snow clearing technology which is observed a cause for inefficient winter road maintenance practices in Kashmir. Finally, the solution is reduced to the combination of strong policy (POLC) and an efficient road weather information system (RWIS) along with technology (TECH) which are mainly responsible for effective WRM practices (see figure 3). The policies lay down different parameters like- minimum accumulation of snow on a particular road for the deployment of a snow removal machine. Usually, the public inconvenience occurs when the snow removing agencies wait for the increase in depth of snow to reach to the laid down depth according to the policy. Meanwhile, the plying traffic compresses the snow with extremely close packing resulting in frost with the plummeting mercury in the evenings. Figure 4 represents a snap shot from a video which shows the inefficient snow removal (undulation) as a result of a wrong policy decision in the City of Edmonton, Canada (Bench 2020). The policy decision has been the restriction of the use of snow removal

Country	POLC	WINX	RWIS	ANTI	TECH	EWRM
Kashmir	0	0	0	1	0	0
China, Netherlands	0	0	1	1	1	1
Canada, France	0	1	1	1	1	1
Japan	1	0	0	1	1	1
Hungary	1	0	1	1	1	1
Italy, Norway	1	1	0	1	1	1
USA, Germany	1	1	1	1	1	1
Outcome: 0						
# Implicants: 2						
polc*rwis	0	Kashmir				
tech	0	Kashmir				
# Solutions: 2						
polc*rwis						
tech						

Figure 3. csQCA Results

Figure 4. Extremely uncomfortable undulation as a result of wrong policy decision(Bench 2020)

machine until the depth reaches 5 cm. The policies also describe the level of service and prioritization

of roads depending upon the traffic volume which are also important factors for effective WRM practices. Next important aspect is the use of road weather information system, which is really a vital parameter to ensure the effective snow removal. Some RWIS provide the real time information to the snow control centres thus ensuring timely clearance of roads of the snow. One more important aspect of winter road maintenance has been observed as use of suitable and apt technology (TECH). A machine which is intended for carrying the troops and loads for military and logistics applications respectively can't deliver as a snow plowing machine. Most of the countries studied in this report have the machinery which has been designed only for the purpose of snow removal. On the contrary, the winter road maintenance in Kashmir is prominently carried out with the help of agricultural tractors and loading trucks which does not deliver in an efficient manner.

4. Conclusion

The effectiveness and efficiency of winter road maintenance is subjected to a host of factors- a robust WRM policy in place, efficient road weather information system and the deployment of suitable and apt technology in the form of snow plowing machines and snow blowers. The robust WRM policy should give due concern to prevailing climatic conditions of a region, appropriate level of service and prioritization of roads, anti-icing treatment, availability of sufficient men and machinery. The road weather information system must be able to provide the real-time snow accumulation data to snow and ice control centers so as to ensure a swift action on their part. Snow clearance machinery should be procured from the manufacturers which design their machines only for the purpose of snow removal. Some countries take utmost care in the use of anti-icing materials for winter road maintenance, given the fragility of environment in presence of some salts, e.g. Hungary keeps a check on the salt levels in the water, so as to ensure sustainability of WRM practices and use of anti-icing materials therein.

4.1 Policy Implications

One of most common factors which is observed in majority of the WRM policies discussed in this paper is road weather information system (RWIS) which helps the snow removal teams by supplying them with real time information about the weather and road conditions in addition to traffic conditions (Sharma, Wu, and Kwon 2021). Snow clearance in Kashmir is solely based on manual procedures except a weather advisory supplied by Indian Meteorological Department, Srinagar. Had the real time information about the road weather conditions been available with the snow control stations, the dispatch of machines and level of service could have been estimated appropriately resulting in effective and efficient WRM operations. When technological factors are considered, the system in Kashmir is lacking many important aspects of standard practices prevalent across the world. The machinery being used for snow removal in Kashmir has been mostly designed for load carrying, agriculture and industry which results in inefficient snow removal operations especially when the snow depth cross 2 feet threshold. There are no set guidelines for the procurement of materials and machines in Kashmir while most of the countries have standard guidelines for doing so e.g. American Association of State Highway and Transportation Officials(AASHTO) in cooperation with the Federal Highway Administration (FHA) under National Cooperative Highway Research Program (NCHRP) issues the recommendations in the form of NCHRP report, for selecting snow and ice control strategies and tactics for a variety of winter maintenance conditions. These rules apply to highways, roads, streets, and other paved surfaces in state and local jurisdictions that carry motor vehicles. The guidelines aid winter maintenance personnel in determining the appropriate level-of-service (LOS)-driven roadway snow and ice control operations, as well as managing snow and ice control resources effectively. State and local highway agency personnel, as well as others involved in snow and ice control, will benefit from the NCHRP report. Anti-icing is not prominent in Kashmir especially pre-salting because the responsibility of antiicing has been entrusted by the

government to civil engineering wing of Public Works Department while the WRM is carried out by mechanical wing, there is always a lack of coordination among the departments which results in non-deployment of anti-icing techniques at the appropriate time which in turn causes a lot of problems like compression of snow by constant plying of traffic especially during ongoing snowfall. The compressed snow fall gets frozen overnight and remains for days together and causes a lot of inconvenience to people travelling through vehicles. The WRM policy for Kashmir should define everything – Level of Service (LoS), advocate for relevant technology, RWIS, anti-icing and pre-salting at appropriate point of time, number of men and machines required based on Winter Severity Index, which needs to be defined in first place. The PWD should be involved in the policy design for WRM taking the feedback from the field units and the implementation should be carried out by the mechanical and civil engineering wings of the department using men and machines. There should be strict law to prevent the people from designing their rooftops in a way that the accumulated snow over the roof does not fall on the road which becomes an impediment in the functioning of machines. The law should prevent the venturing out of the people from their homes and plying of public and private transport in the event of snowfall for a fixed period of time to give room to the snow removing men and machines.

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